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SCREENING AND PREVENTION OF DELIRIUM IN THE INTENSIVE CARE UNIT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Delirium is a common, life-threatening condition that occurs in the intensive care unit (ICU) and results in increased ICU mortality, ICU length of stay (LOS), restraint usage, and ventilation days. Improving nursing awareness of delirium is essential to improve safety and quality of care. Delirium prevention is shifting from a pharmacological to a non-pharmacological approach that nurses can independently implement. This project employed an evidence-based nurse-led non-pharmacological delirium prevention bundle (DPB) to reduce the incidence of delirium in a community ICU. A pre-post design evaluated the effectiveness of a DPB consisting of reorientation, early mobility, and sleep promotion. Nurses received education on the DPB through in-services and nurse huddles. Outcomes measured were obtained from the Electronic Health Record data and included delirium incidence using the Confusion Assessment Method-Intensive Care Unit (CAM-ICU), compliance with DPB, ICU LOS, restraint usage, ventilation days, and ICU mortality. The nurse-perceived delirium barriers survey measured knowledge deficits, self-confidence, time constraints, and delirium awareness. The DPB significantly reduced delirium incidence by 55%. DPB compliance was optimal. Restraint usage and ICU mortality improved, while ICU LOS and ventilation days did not change. This project demonstrated that a nurse-led non-pharmacological DPB reduced delirium incidence and improved clinical outcomes in a community hospital ICU. Ultimately, nurse education increased ICU nurses' competency and confidence in preventing delirium.

Keywords: delirium, prevention bundle, Intensive Care Unit, outcomes, barriers, education, non-pharmacological, mechanical ventilation, restraints, Intensive Care Unit length of stay, mortality.

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Background

Critically ill patients in Intensive Care Units (ICUs) are at high risk for delirium, which hampers recovery. Delirium is an acute brain failure that requires screening and prevention. The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5) defines delirium as an acute confusion state characterized by cognitive disorders, disturbance in attention and awareness, abnormal levels of consciousness, and fluctuating course (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Typically, delirium develops within hours after admission. The brain damage seen in delirium can be attributed to neuroinflammation, neurotransmitter dysregulation, and disruption of brain metabolism (Haggstrom et al., 2017).

Recognition of delirium among ICU patients is essential for safe care delivery. Brummel et al. (2014) reported that delirium is often missed and remains substantially under-recognized. Under-recognition of delirium is due to a lack of appreciation of the symptoms of delirium and failure to recognize the significance of delirium in the ICU. Additionally, Inouye et al. (2001) reported that recognizing delirium could be challenging to identify among patients aged 80 or older, those with hypoactive delirium, and those with vision impairments or dementia. The waxing and waning course of delirium also makes identification challenging. The core symptoms of delirium are also confused with other psychiatric conditions (Mart et al., 2021).

Consequently, delirium is frequently neglected, not monitored, or not discussed during multidisciplinary ICU rounds (Morandi et al., 2017). Under-recognition is an independent predictor of numerous adverse outcomes. Thus, early recognition of delirium is essential because the more days patients spend in a state of delirium, the higher the risk of death (Duprey et al., 2020). Klein-Klouwenberg et al. (2014) reported that patients spending more than two days in delirium increases their odds of mortality.

Delirium is especially prevalent among patients in ICUs (Marcantonio, 2017). The incidence of delirium in the ICU is between 15% to 80% (Inouye, 2006; Salluh et al., 2015). Among mechanically ventilated patients, the incidence of delirium is between 50% to 89% (Marcantonio, 2017), while in post-operative conditions, it is between 15% to 53% (Pisani et al., 2003).

Delirium is associated with numerous adverse clinical outcomes, such as longer ICU length of stay (LOS), increased ICU mortality, prolonged ventilation days, and higher cost of care. Ely et al. (2004) reported that a diagnosis of delirium adds approximately ten days to the patient's mean LOS. Each additional day a patient experiences delirium, their risk of death increases by 10% (Barr et al., 2013; Ely et al., 2004). A meta-analysis reported that patients with delirium were six times more likely to experience prolonged mechanical ventilation. The extended hospital LOS explains the increased healthcare costs associated with delirium (Oberai et al., 2017). Managing a patient with delirium is between \$800 to \$14,000. Due to extended LOS and long-term institutionalization, the economic impact of delirium in the United States has been evaluated to be more than 164 billion dollars annually (Inouye, 2006). Awareness of the costs and complications can be an impetus to prevent delirium.

In addition to physical complications, delirium is associated with long-term psychosocial impairment (Barr et al., 2013; Wolters et al., 2014). Marcantonio (2017) reported that 25% to 78% of delirium patients have a long-term psycho-social impairment. Patients who experience delirium are described as fearful and ineffective in building rapport post-discharge. Even after delirium is resolved, some patients experience impaired psychosocial functioning, which can impact the patient's quality of life (Inouye et al., 2020). Once home, patients with delirium may

experience difficulties with self-care routines (Palakshappa et al., 2021). To address the outcomes of delirium, it is essential to understand the causes contributing to its development.

The cause of delirium is multifactorial (Bettelli et al., 2017) and related to acute illnesses, injuries (hip fractures), stress, changes in settings, or side effects of drugs (McKenzie et al., 2020). Delirium is due to the interaction between risk factors. The risk factors are modifiable and non-modifiable (Appendix A). The modifiable risk factors include hearing and vision impairment, immobilization due to restraints or catheters, medications (sedatives, narcotics, antipsychotic, anticholinergic), withdrawal of alcohol or drugs, acute neurological impairments (stroke, meningitis), intercurrent illnesses (dehydration, poor nutrition, anemia, post-operative, pain, hospital environment), and severe sleep deprivation. Non-modifiable risk factors include a history of delirium, dementia, age 65 and older, multiple comorbidities, being male, and chronic liver or kidney failure. The modifiable risk factors of delirium are amenable to preventative interventions (Palakshappa et al., 2021).

Since delirium is linked to numerous causes and can result from interactions between the patient and the ICU environment, multi-component interventions addressing modifiable causes can be bundled together to mitigate delirium (Hee et al., 2021; Trogrlić et al., 2019). Specifically, non-pharmacological prevention strategies have been shown to reduce the adverse outcomes of delirium (Hshieh et al., 2015; Reston et al., 2013). A bundle is multi-faceted, but its individual components are synergistic and linked together to improve care. Compliance with all the components of the bundle is an essential strategy to reduce adverse outcomes (Barnes-Daly et al., 2017).

Nurses spend more hours with patients than other healthcare providers; thus, they play a key role and are uniquely situated to implement and evaluate non-pharmacological delirium

bundles. Without a physician's order, nurses can independently implement non-pharmacological prevention strategies to reduce the risk of delirium (Inouye et al., 2014). It has been reported that nurses can only identify delirium in 19% of cases, limiting their role in preventing the condition (Inouye et al., 2001; Marcantonio, 2017). Raising awareness of delirium among nurses is essential to fulfilling the role of preventing delirium.

Delirium among ICU patients is recognized as a potentially preventable complication of critical care illness (Inouye et al., 2014). As a preventable condition, delirium should be targeted for interventions to prevent its complications. To avoid the plethora of poor outcomes associated with delirium, nurses must initiate early identification, identify reversible causes, and implement appropriate interventions to prevent them.

Statement of Purpose

The purpose of this evidenced-based DNP project was to implement and evaluate a nurse-led non-pharmacological delirium prevention bundle in a 32-bed ICU community hospital.

Supporting Framework

The Iowa Model was used to guide this project because it facilitates knowledge transfer and guides the translation of research into patient care (Titler et al., 2001). The Primary Author (PA) sought permission to use the Iowa Model (Appendix B) from the University of Iowa Hospitals. The problem-solving nature of the Iowa Model (Appendix C) provides the methods used for investigating a problem, developing a plan to address it, interpreting the findings, and evaluating the change. Additionally, Doody et al. (2011) reported its use in numerous critical care settings. The Iowa Model has ten steps (Appendix D).

Selection of a Topic

In this project, inconsistencies in the prevention practices for delirium in the ICU were the triggers. The ICU nurses' limited knowledge of delirium prevention interfered with their ability to deliver optimum care. The Awakening, Breathing, Coordination (or choice of sedation), Delirium monitoring and management, Early mobility, and Family involvement (ABCDEF) bundle, along with the Pain, Agitation/Sedation, Delirium, Immobility, and Sleep Disruption (PADIS) guideline from the Society of Critical Medicine (Devlin et al., 2008) recommended strategies to identify and prevent delirium in the ICU. The components of these bundles were modified and implemented to meet the project's purpose.

State the Question/Aim

This DNP project aimed to implement and evaluate an evidence-based multicomponent delirium prevention bundle to reduce the incidence of delirium and optimize clinical outcomes in the ICU.

Priority for the Organization

The actual incidence of delirium in the ICU at the project setting was unknown because the data were not available. Nonetheless, clinical leaders believed the incidence of delirium to be more than 30%. To significantly decrease delirium, ICU clinical leaders prioritized delirium prevention and suggested that the PA and her ICU team initiate a delirium screening and prevention program.

Team Formation

A multidisciplinary team of stakeholders, including the PA, intensivists, ICU nurses, respiratory therapists (RTs), quality coordinators, physical therapists (PTs), and information technology (IT) consultants, collaborated to initiate and implement this project.

Assemble, Appraise, and Synthesize the Body of Evidence

The PA conducted a literature review and analyzed existing delirium guidelines from the American Nurse Association (ANA) and the Society of Critical Medicine to develop a delirium prevention bundle to implement in the ICU.

Is there Sufficient Evidence?

A bundle of activities identified from the literature and endorsed by the Society of Critical Medicine and the American Association of Critical Care Nurses to improve the screening and prevention of delirium was selected. This bundle included the Confusion Assessment Method-ICU (CAM-ICU) and non-pharmacological interventions to prevent delirium. Although it was essential to consider all interventions that could have been employed to address delirium, only non-pharmacological and nurse-led interventions (interventions that did not require a physician's order) were included in the delirium prevention bundle.

Design and Pilot the Practice Change

This step consisted of collecting baseline demographics and outcome data such as incidence of delirium, compliance with the implementation of the DPB, ICU LOS, ICU mortality, ventilation days, and restraint usage. Resources and support from upper management and administration were crucial in this step, as their buy-in was essential for successful implementation. The evidence from the literature was presented to ICU staff and focused on the benefits and strengths of delirium identification and prevention. The delirium implementation team engaged the ICU staff and developed a strategy to obtain feedback for the evaluation of the success of this project. Prior to the initiation of this project, frontline ICU nurses were trained to use the CAM-ICU screening tool (Appendix E); however, its use was inconsistent among ICU nurses, which made it difficult to measure and evaluate the incidence of delirium. During the

project, ICU nurses were again trained on the CAM-ICU and were educated on the implementation of the Delirium Prevention Bundle (DPB) (Appendix F).

Is the Change Appropriate for Adoption in Practice?

Following the implementation of the DPB and outcome data evaluation, the delirium implementation team assessed if the change was appropriate for adoption in the ICU. Barriers that interfered with the adoption of the DNP project were identified using the pre- and post-education nurse perceived delirium barriers surveys. Barriers such as deficits in education, time constraint, and lack of awareness were addressed. Leadership or management support, education and training where needed, and unit champions were considered to address the barriers to implementing the CAM-ICU screening tool and the DPB.

Integrate and Sustain the Practice Change

The team integrated and sustained the practice change by engaging key personnel such as intensivists, RT, PT, frontline nurses, and clinical leaders. The successful contribution of ICU nurses in implementing the DPB was highlighted since they spent the most time with patients and were responsible for the continued implementation of the practice change. Post-implementation data were reviewed against baseline data to assess the success of implementing the practice change. Creating a shared vision for preventing delirium was communicated. Annual CAM-ICU competency assessment and DPB competency implementation were planned to sustain the change. Moreover, to improve stakeholder buy-in, the incidence rate of delirium was provided to the ICU staff so they could appreciate their effort in reducing and preventing delirium. At staff meetings and daily huddles, the PA provided updates, opportunities for improvement, and progress related to the initiative. Embedding the CAM-ICU and the delirium prevention bundle in the EHR was beneficial for sustainability. With any practice change, there

may be resistance, and this was addressed using meetings and open discussions about the change the project created in the ICU.

Disseminate the Change

The findings were disseminated and shared with the stakeholders. To improve and make care delivery safer, it was planned to initiate delirium prevention in the Emergency Department (ED), medical-surgical, and step-down units of the hospital. Successful outcomes, such as reducing the incidence of delirium and associated cost savings of the DPB, were shared.

Review of Literature

Overview

A literature review was conducted to select delirium identification and prevention articles for adults in the ICU. The electronic databases searched included PubMed and CINAHL. The university librarian was consulted on conducting a thorough literature search for relevant articles. Articles were included if published between 2000 and 2022 in peer-reviewed journals and pertained to adults 18 years or older. Articles were selected regardless of their geographical location if they were written in English. Book chapters, conference abstracts, or opinion papers were excluded. Titles and abstracts were reviewed for key terms to determine the inclusion of the article. Key terms included: CAM-ICU, delirium, delirium protocol, delirium prevention, delirium bundle, incidence of delirium, intensive care unit, critical care, restraints, mechanical ventilation, ICU length of stay, mortality, and outcomes. Additional terms searched were evidence-based practice, orientation, family, mobility, sleep, and ventilation days. The search also included a manual examination of the reference sections of selected articles to identify additional articles for the literature review. The literature review was divided into the following topics: an overview of delirium, screening for delirium, non-pharmacological prevention strategies, and delirium education.

It is essential to understand the different symptoms of delirium and the difficulties associated with its identification. There are three clinical subtypes of delirium: hyperactive, hypoactive, and mixed. A patient with hyperactive delirium experiences agitation, restlessness, and disorientation. These overt symptoms make this form of delirium easy to recognize. On the other hand, patients with hypoactive delirium appear to be quiet and lethargic (Smutler et al., 2019). The hypoactive form of delirium is difficult to detect since the patient is not presenting

with visible signs and symptoms. A patient suffering from mixed delirium presents with both hyper and hypoactive delirium symptoms. Patients with mixed delirium are also difficult to identify because they vacillate between being lethargic and hyperactive. Although delirium is known as a hazard, it is frequently unrecognized and underappreciated in the ICU. Delirium identification in the ICU may go unrecognized in 66% to 84% of patients (Marcantonio, 2017).

Delirium is associated with prolonged mechanical ventilation and length of stay (LOS), increased mortality, restraint usage, and costs. Numerous co-morbidities, such as dementia and cardiovascular conditions, can increase the risk of delirium (Zall et al., 2015). Among mechanically ventilated patients, the prevalence is between 50% to 70% (Krewulak et al., 2018). Thus, the identification and treatment of delirium among patients in the ICU are important to address as this awareness helps to decrease adverse outcomes such as ICU LOS and the number of ventilation days.

Over time practice guidelines have been developed to mitigate delirium and improve ICU morbidity and mortality. The ABCDEF bundle is a set of evidence-based practices created to standardize care in the ICU and improve morbidity and mortality rates (Marra et al., 2017). It has undergone many iterations over the years due to its complexity. In 2018, a guideline for the prevention and management of Pain, Agitation/Sedation, Delirium, Immobility, and Sleep Disruption (PADIS) was developed for adult patients in the ICU (Collinworth et al., 2021). The PADIS is a framework used to reduce delirium and provides modifications to the ICU environment that contribute to it. The ABCDEF bundle, a multidisciplinary patient-centered approach based on the PADIS guidelines was integrated into ICU practices (Collinworth et al., 2021). Additionally, the ABCDEF bundle and the PADIS guideline (Barr et al., 2013) are multi-component strategies to prevent prolonged hospitalizations and mitigate delirium symptoms.

Many organizations do not implement all bundle components but tailor them to address specific risk factors.

There is ample evidence to indicate that a multi-component bundle approach to the prevention of delirium decreases adverse outcomes (Hshieh et al., 2015; Inouye et al., 2014; Rivosecchi et al., 2016; Shehabi et al., 2018). When a set of evidence-based interventions to prevent delirium are bundled together, there is synergy between the different components of the bundle to improve the effectiveness of delirium prevention (Clarkson, 2013; Mart et al., 2019). Moreover, individually, each of the components of the bundle has been associated with a reduction in delirium incidence and numerous improved outcomes, including shorter LOS, reduced ventilation days, and improved survival (Barnes-Daly et al., 2017). The bundles identified in the literature included interventions focusing on the assessment and prevention of delirium. Appropriate delirium screening tools have been identified as a necessary component in all bundles. A nurse-led multi-component delirium bundle reported in the literature consists of non-pharmacological interventions such as reorientation, early mobility, and sleep promotion. Non-pharmacological delirium interventions as a bundle have been found to shorten the duration of delirium from 4 to 3 days (odds ratio 0.64, 95 % CI 0.46-0.87; Oberai et al., 2017). The use of DPB has been shown to significantly reduce ICU LOS (DiSabatino et al., 2017; Hee et al., 2021; Rivosecchi et al., 2016).

Routine Screening for Delirium Using CAM-ICU

There are numerous delirium screening tools available for use in the ICU; however, the most widely used is the CAM-ICU (Ely et al., 2001). The original CAM was developed for psychiatric clinicians to screen for delirium in non-ICU settings, while the CAM-ICU was explicitly designed for use in the ICU. The CAM-ICU is a validated, shortened version of the

CAM developed for nonverbal, mechanically ventilated patients (Grover et al., 2013). CAM-ICU has a sensitivity of 94% to 100%, a specificity of 90% to 95%, and a positive predictive accuracy of 91% to 94% (Ely et al., 2001). The CAM-ICU has interrater reliability ranging from 0.81 to 1.00. Convergent agreement with other mental status tests, including the Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE), was established (Wong et al., 2010).

Administration of the CAM-ICU typically takes less than three minutes to complete with formal training. Adherence to the processes described in the training manual (www.icudelirium.org) is recommended to optimize diagnostic accuracy (Wong et al., 2010). The sensitivity of the CAM-ICU decreases markedly if the assessor is not formally trained (Inouye, 2006). ICU nurses often find it challenging to integrate the CAM-ICU screening tool into their routine patient care practices, and thus screening tools are underutilized in the ICU (Neufeld et al., 2016). A barrier to CAM-ICU use is the perceived time needed to complete the formal cognitive assessment (Haley et al., 2019). Because of time constraints, nurses reported abbreviating the CAM-ICU, which only decreased its sensitivity (Wei et al., 2008), resulting in missed recognition of subtle symptoms associated with hypoactive delirium.

Non-Pharmacological Prevention Strategies for Delirium

Delirium is seldom due to one factor but instead results from the interaction of numerous patient and hospital risk factors. The risk factors related to the development of delirium are modifiable and non-modifiable. Immobility, disorientation, and sleep deprivation are modifiable risk factors that respond best to non-pharmacological multicomponent prevention interventions (Devlin et al., 2008). Other common risk factors, such as constipation, urinary tract infections, and surgical pain, may respond best to pharmacological interventions (Inouye, 2014). Another modifiable factor beneficial for managing delirium is the ICU environment. No windows,

excessive noise, absent view of the outside nature, sleep pattern disruption, isolation, and immobilization can contribute to delirium (Chanques et al., 2018). Identifying and addressing these risk factors is essential to address delirium. Most ICU nurses lack knowledge and awareness of modifiable risk factors contributing to delirium (Sharma et al., 2012). To reduce the risks of developing delirium, ICU nurses should implement a proactive rather than a reactive approach to alleviate the modifiable risk factors.

ICU clinicians have traditionally used a pharmacological approach to prevent delirium. However, recent literature and the Society of Critical Care Medicine guidelines have reported avoiding routine use of a pharmacological approach using medications such as benzodiazepine or antipsychotics (Andersen-Ranberg et al., 2022; Mart et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2020). A meta-analysis also concluded that a pharmacological approach did not significantly reduce the duration or severity of delirium, LOS, or mortality (Neufeld et al., 2016). Collet et al. (2018) reported that half of the delirium patients received haloperidol even though there is little evidence to use this medication. Inouye et al. (2020) did not recommend administering antipsychotics during the implementation of delirium prevention. Likewise, the use of benzodiazepines in the ICU has been reported to be a risk factor for delirium and was linked to increased ICU mortality and days on mechanical ventilation (Shehabi et al., 2018). Consequently, as there are few pharmacological options for treating delirium, the cornerstone approach is to use non-pharmacological strategies (Mart et al., 2021).

Although evidence-based bundles such as ABCDEF are endorsed by critical care societies such as the Society of Critical Care Medicine, providers do not implement all the components of the bundles (Marra et al., 2017). Bundles, especially with numerous components, are perceived to be complex due to factors such as workload, lack of self-confidence, difficulty

in implementing the components, and perceived safety during ambulation. Boehm et al. (2017) reported that reducing workload and perceived implementation difficulty can facilitate bundle compliance. For example, if nurses believed that delirium prevention bundles could be effective, the implementation may improve. Bundle implementation can also be improved by addressing factors including bundle difficulty, confidence in executing the bundle, clarity of policies and protocols, coordination within the multidisciplinary team, autonomy of nurses, reduction of time constraints, and access to resources.

Reorientation

Many patients become disoriented in the ICU due to medications, hypoxia, dehydration, hypoglycemia, and infection. Some studies suggest the prevalence of disorientation is as high as 70% (Inouye et al., 2014; Krewulak et al., 2018). The risk for delirium significantly increases when patients become disoriented (Inouye et al., 2014). Thus, many delirium bundles include interventions to regularly reorient patients to person, time, and place. Mitchell et al. (2018) reported that cognitive and memory stimulation using visuals could significantly reduce delirium. Visuals include family photographs, discussing family life, and reminiscing about life events. This is enhanced when family members are used to conveying the information. Constant reorientation interventions should also include updating whiteboards, clocks, and calendars (Faraklas et al., 2013). These interventions are easy to implement but require that the nurse is vigilant in their practices.

Columbo et al. (2012) showed in an observational study that a bedside reorientation strategy significantly correlated with a reduction in delirium. The researchers identified several reorientation strategies that were easy to implement. Calling patients by their first name was an identified reorientation strategy. Orienting the patient to night and day by opening and closing

the blinds can help reorient the patient to the time of day. Providing the patient with information about the ICU and emphasizing care expectations helped to reorient the patient. Providing the patient with cognitive stimulation, such as asking them their name and names of relatives, also helped with reorientation.

Reorientation is a simple but robust intervention to deliver structured information to critically ill patients on an ongoing basis. Since reorientation is nurse-focused, it has the potential to be synergistic with other non-pharmacological interventions (Columbo et al., 2012).

Implementing reorientation interventions is low cost, which makes it efficient in preventing delirium. In addition to reorientation, early mobility is another component that prevents delirium.

Early Mobility

Early mobility, part of the PADIS guideline and the ABCDEF bundle, reduces ICU-acquired delirium (Dirkes et al., 2019; Karadas et al., 2016). Early mobility is defined as having patients engaged in active exercises from day two to day five in the ICU. Early mobility consists of a series of activities ranging from a passive range of motion to ambulation with assistance.

When working together, multidisciplinary mobility teams, which include PTs, RTs, and nurses, can reduce delirium and decrease a patient's LOS (Engel et al., 2013). The use of early mobility strategies can decrease the odds of developing delirium by 55% (OR, 0.55; 95% CI, 0.33 -.93; $p=0.03$; Balas et al., 2013).

Despite the importance of early mobility, it continues to be underutilized as a delirium prevention strategy in ICUs (Balas et al., 2013). Moreover, only 39% of ICU staff reported using early mobility for ventilated patients within the first 48-72 hours (Miller et al., 2015). Mobility is safe and feasible (Sricharoenchai et al., 2014) to use with critically ill patients and had shown to decrease days of delirium, duration of mechanical ventilation, and ICU LOS (Liang et al., 2021;

Mart et al., 2021). Nurses are expected to perform the daily safety screening before mobilizing the patient.

Sleep Promotion

Sleep is essential for the well-being and health of ICU patients. Numerous studies have established that sleep deprivation adversely affects many physiological systems, such as respiratory and cognitive function (Lu et al., 2019; Pisani et al., 2020). Approximately 80% of ICU patients experience sleep deprivation during hospitalization (Kamdar et al., 2013). Some critical care clinicians have not considered sleeping a priority for ICU patients. However, evidence shows that sleep disruptions can cause circadian rhythm changes that negatively impact the patient, which increases the risk of delirium (Kamdar et al., 2013).

Several environmental factors can disrupt a patient's sleep, including high levels of noise from alarms and ventilators, patient care activities, and ambient lighting (Lu et al., 2019). The Society of Critical Care Medicine (SCCM) recommends the Clinical Practice Guideline for the Management of PADIS to optimize the patients' environment by controlling the day/night cycle, limiting noise and lights, and clustering activities. The use of earplugs and eye masks has been shown to reduce the incidence of delirium (Hu et al., 2015; Litton et al., 2016). Sleep promotion, reorientation, and early mobility are strategies used to reduce delirium; however, staff must be educated on these strategies.

Delirium Prevention Bundle Education

A structured ICU educational delirium strategy effectively enhances knowledge translation, improves delirium recognition skills, and prevention practices, and reduces the incidence of delirium (Blevins et al., 2018). Early recognition of delirium by nurses requires specific knowledge and skills. However, nurses only recognized 35% of delirious days, while

intensivists performed even lower, with only 28% of days with delirium identified (Inouye et al., 2001). Clearly, the identification of delirium is low, with clinicians missing three out of four delirium cases due to a lack of delirium knowledge and/or standardized screening practices (Van Eijk et al., 2009). Identification of hypoactive and/or mixed delirium is especially low (Inouye et al., 2001). Confidence in screening skills and delirium knowledge was reported to improve care practices in the ICU (Devlin et al., 2018).

Educating nurses about the DPB and CAM-ICU through didactic training may prevent delirium (Hsing, 2021). Didactic training, including videos, one-on-one education, role-play scenarios, and bedside demonstrations are methods for educating nurses on delirium prevention. Bedside demonstrations on how to use the CAM-ICU and implementation of a delirium prevention bundle have been shown to increase nurse knowledge and improve their self-confidence (Hsing, 2021). Clinical case scenarios, slide demonstrations, and workshops have been effective educational strategies (Shao et al., 2021). These strategies effectively improve competence and performance, enhancing patient care (Hsing, 2021). Despite the known benefit of recommendations such as ABCDEF and PADIS bundles, providers rarely use them (Ista et al., 2021). One reason for this poor adoption and dissemination was related to knowledge transfer and the complexity of the bundles, which can be improved by high-quality education.

In summary, the ICU environment contributes significantly to the risk factors that can cause delirium. This literature review strongly supported using the CAM-ICU tool to screen delirium in ICU patients (Grover et al., 2013; Wong et al., 2010). The CAM-ICU is a validated screening tool with high sensitivity and specificity. Identifying and reducing modifiable risk factors reduces the incidence of delirium. Implementing a multicomponent prevention strategy significantly reduces the incidence of delirium among critically ill patients. Reorientation, early

mobility, and sleep promotion are prevention strategies to reduce the incidence of delirium and improve the quality of care (Hee et al., 2021; Inouye et al., 2014). Despite being challenging, the implementation of a multicomponent delirium prevention bundle decreases the odds of developing delirium (Dirkes et al., 2019). A structured educational and training program effectively enhances ICU nurses' competency in delirium prevention (Blevins et al., 2018).

Methods

This evidence-based practice project implemented clinical practice guidelines and evaluated the effects of a non-pharmacological nurse-led delirium prevention bundle on delirium incidence and other clinical outcomes using a pre-post design. This section describes the setting and samples, ethical considerations, outcome measures, phases (procedures), and evaluation plan.

Setting

The project was conducted at a 32-bed adult medical and surgical ICU in a 232-bed community hospital located in Southern California. The average bed occupancy rate was 50%, with an average daily census of 16. Moreover, both the census and staffing did not change during the project. Depending on the patient's acuity, the ICU was staffed at a 1:2 or 1:1 ratio. The nurses worked, on average, thirty-six hours weekly. Nearly 30% of the patients were post-operative cardiothoracic patients or had undergone cardiac procedures. The average length of stay for patients in the ICU was four days. The ICU team was comprised of a Director of Nursing, six clinical managers, 52 nurses, two physiotherapists, three RTs, and four intensivists.

Samples and Participants

There were two samples in this DNP project: ICU patient participants and ICU nurse participants. Convenience sampling was used for both. All ICU nurses employed in the ICU and all patients admitted during the project timeframe who met eligibility criteria were included in this project. The inclusion criteria for ICU patient participants were: 18 years or older and expected to stay in the ICU for at least 24 hours. Patient participants were excluded from the project if they were: admitted with delirium, died or were discharged within 24 hours, had an admitting diagnosis related to neurological or central nervous system injuries (e.g., coma), had a

Richmond Agitation Sedation Score (RASS) score -4 or less, were aphasic, had psychiatric auditory hallucinations, profound deafness, primary dementia, or were at the end of life or on comfort measures (exclusive palliative care) upon admission to the ICU. The PA and unit champions identified potential patient participants during daily rounds and after reviewing eligibility criteria in the EHR. Patient participants' flow during this project is shown in Appendix G Figure 3.

Institutional Review Board/Ethics

Institutional review board (IRB) approval from California State University, Long Beach, was secured before the project was implemented (Appendix H). Patient participant data were stored on a secured drive on the hospital computer, which was created specifically for this project. The PA and the unit champions were the only people with access to this dataset to maintain confidentiality. No patient participant or nurse identification information was used during this process. No risks were associated with participating for patients or nurse participants. Those who participated in the project might have benefited from the delirium prevention measures. Nurse participants signed informed consent before completing the nurse-perceived delirium barriers surveys (Appendix I & Appendix J).

Outcomes and Measures

The primary outcomes in this project were 1) ICU delirium incidence evaluated by the CAM-ICU and 2) Compliance with the delirium prevention bundle (DPB). A patient had delirium if the CAM-ICU was positive for at least one day, regardless of the number of days delirium was experienced. Delirium incidence was calculated by the total number of patient participants experiencing delirium divided by the total number of patient participants meeting the eligibility criteria. Compliance with the DPB was determined by reviewing the DPB

documentation in the EHR. Each separate component of the bundle (reorientation, early mobility, and sleep promotion) was measured independently, as well as the measurement of the completion of the entire bundle (including all three components). A complete bundle performance was defined as having all three components of the bundle documented on any given day in the EHR (100% of the bundle versus anything less). Partial bundle documentation was defined as patient participants who did not receive the three components of the bundle on any given day. De-identified patient data were extracted from the EHR and entered directly into an Excel spreadsheet by the PA and unit champions.

This project evaluated patients' delirium when they were fully awake. When a patient was in a coma (RASS -4 or -5), the patient was designated as unable to be assessed for delirium and was excluded from the project. For this project, delirium was noted as a binary outcome (present or absent) based on a positive or negative CAM-ICU assessment.

The secondary outcomes included ICU LOS, ICU mortality, ventilation days, restraint usage, and nurse-perceived delirium barriers. Patient participants were considered to have an ICU day if they were present in an ICU bed at midnight. The average ICU LOS was the total number of ICU days (measured from ICU admission date until ICU discharge date or death date) divided by the total number of patients (Appendix K). The average ventilation days were defined as the total number of days patients were mechanically ventilated divided by the total number of patients on mechanical ventilators. Restraint usage was recorded as either “yes” for the presence of restraints and “no” for the absence of restraints. Any patient participant who expired while in the ICU was considered an ICU mortality. Furthermore, nurses completed a process evaluation using the nurse-perceived delirium barriers survey.

Procedures

This project was performed in two phases. Phase 1 (October 2 to October 30, 2022) identified patient baseline demographics (age, ICU admission date, sex, race/ethnicity, and comorbidities) and outcomes (delirium incidence, ICU LOS, restraint usage, ICU mortality, and ventilation days). During phase one, routine patient care was provided; there were no standardized policies or education on delirium (Appendix L). For example, at the discretion of the PTs, passive/active exercises or out-of-bed ambulation were delivered on an ad hoc basis. All patient participants were screened for delirium using the CAM-ICU every 12-hour shift or whenever it was deemed that the patient had a change in mental status.

After baseline data were collected, nurses were invited to complete the first nurse-perceived delirium barriers survey before the DPB education between October 21st to October 30th, 2022. Nurses were again requested to complete the same nurse-perceived delirium barriers survey a second time after the education from December 7th to December 16th, 2022. Anonymous survey respondent tracking using the last four digits of nurse participants' phone numbers allowed the PA and the unit champions to associate individual responses with the corresponding respondents. The 8-question nurse-perceived delirium barriers survey was administered to evaluate the nurses' attitudes toward perceived barriers to delirium screening and DPB implementation. The surveys analyzed knowledge deficit, self-confidence, time constraints/workload, and delirium awareness during the implementation of DPB. This survey was adapted and modified from studies reported in the literature (Eastwood et al., 2011; Law et al., 2012). A hard copy of this survey and demographic questions were delivered to all ICU nurses. The nurse participants were given ten days to return their completed surveys. The surveys were answered anonymously and voluntarily. The nurses were reminded in person, and an email

was sent to all ICU nurse participants regarding the ten-day timeline for completion of the survey. Questions were answered using a 5-point Likert scale. Gift cards were given to the nurses to acknowledge their time and gratitude for their participation in the survey. The following section describes the contents of the education provided to ICU staff.

From October 31st, 2022, to November 9th, 2022, before DPB implementation, the PA and the unit champions provided a 30-minute mandatory education on the DPB. The delirium education was based on the review of the literature. It encompassed features of delirium, recognition of modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors, symptoms of hypoactive and hyperactive forms of delirium, safety screening for mobility, and how to implement the delirium prevention components of the bundle. Improving the education of nurses was crucial to enhancing the recognition of delirium and the implementation of the DPB (Blevins et al., 2018).

The multimodal delirium education consisted of PowerPoint presentations, posters, case studies, and videos. How to use the CAM-ICU was also reinforced. Implementation of the DPB without an order from a physician was integrated into the usual daily routine care of patients. The PA and unit champions also provided ongoing education and bedside training with return demonstration until all the ICU nurses were proficient. Educational and interactive videos were used to reinforce the training and were accessible on the hospital intranet website. An educational resource binder consisting of the algorithm of CAM-ICU screening, the components of the DPB, and supporting studies were provided to unit champions and available in the unit for consultation. Delirium education pamphlets in English and Spanish were provided to patients and families (Appendix M). After reviewing the complexity, potential cost, and barriers to implementing the DPB, the delirium implementation team enacted a policy for implementation. A copy of the policy was also distributed to the ICU staff.

In Phase 2 (November 10th to December 8th, 2022), ICU nurses started implementing the evidence-based non-pharmacological DPB consisting of three components: reorientation, early mobility, and sleep promotion. These three components were chosen from the author's literature review (Appendix F). Information technology consultants worked with the PA to embed documentation of the DPB and CAM-ICU into the EHR to facilitate adoption as a standard of care. Modifying the EHR included adding tabs for documentation of the three components of the DPB and the result of the CAM-ICU. This modification was intended to allow easy monitoring and improved compliance rate. Nurses were provided additional training to document delirium screening and DPB in the EHR.

After completing a safety screening (Appendix N), each component of the bundle was initiated by nurses in collaboration with the interprofessional team consisting of PTs, physicians, and RTs. For the implementation of early mobility, a team approach was essential; thus, the PTs, RTs, and ICU nurses collaborated to mobilize the patient. Unit champions alerted the nurses when bundle components were due for implementation. The PA and the unit champions rounded daily, used a checklist, and helped overcome barriers. The delirium implementation team analyzed any component that was difficult to execute, as well as progress, improvement opportunities, and process changes. The nurse perceived delirium barriers and feedback were discussed during nurse huddles and rounds to facilitate implementation and improve buy-in. The CAM-ICU screening and DPB implementation were integrated into the annual nursing competency program and orientation for new nurses.

In Phase 2, data were collected on identical patient demographics and outcomes as in Phase 1. A complete list of data collected from ICU patients is included in Table 7 (Appendix O). All data were entered into an Excel spreadsheet. To avoid cross-over data contamination, no

delirium data were collected for the ten days, between October 31st, 2022, to November 9th, 2022. The project was implemented for three months (Appendix P).

The PA-trained unit champions collect patient participants' data gathered from the EHR. The EHR was used to document each component of the DPB per shift (Appendix Q). The PA and unit champions conducted chart audits from the EHR and during patient rounds to evaluate documentation accuracy. Consistent compliance with DPB interventions was difficult to implement because of the timing of sleep promotion activities (Appendix R for bundle compliance tool). This was due to the ongoing activities that occur within the ICU as part of daily operations such as change of shift, admissions and discharges and codes or any other emergencies. The following section describes the three components of the DPB.

Reorientation

Reorientation involves helping the patient to increase their awareness of their surroundings. Nurses used a Script of Messages (Appendix S (English & Spanish versions)) to reorient patients to their environment. The reorientation conversation was designed to enhance sensory stimulation and cognition. The SoMs included calling patients by their names and informing them of the date, time, and place. This communication was verbal and written on the whiteboard, which was in front of the patient's bed. The patient's assigned nurse explained the reasons for their hospitalization and treatment. The nurse placed a clock in front of the patient, and if required, patients were provided access to their glasses and hearing aids during daylight hours. The nursing staff advised the family to be a partner in the reorientation plan. Both English and Spanish-speaking family members were encouraged to read the SoMs. A laminated checklist was attached to the patient's whiteboard as a reminder to reorient them daily. The SoMs were in English but translated into Spanish by a certified translator and offered to Spanish-speaking

patients and their families. Implementing the SoMs did not take longer than two minutes and was written at a 6th-grade reading level. Moreover, the nurses read the SoMs every three hours during the daytime, beginning at 7 AM and ending at 4 PM. This timeframe provided three reorientation conversations with the patients daily.

Early Mobility

After the safety screen, the nurses initiated an early mobility protocol for all patients admitted to the ICU (Appendix N). The multi-disciplinary team supported the implementation of early mobility. The physical therapist director actively engaged and supported the education of safe body mechanics. The early mobility protocol included the following: the frequent turning of bed-bound patients, completing active and passive range of motion exercises, assisting the patient in sitting on the edge of the bed, active transfer to a chair, and passive ambulation. To promote mobility, restraints were minimized, and unnecessary catheters and lines were removed. The amount and types of exercises were tailored to the individual patient based on their clinical conditions. The PTs and the ICU nurse supervised all active ambulation. Ongoing daily bedside coaching and unit huddles improved nurses' expertise, reinforced the implementation of the early mobility protocol, and assured practice change. Before the start of the project, the facility did not have a mobility protocol in place to proactively ambulate patients. Post-DPB implementation, the early mobility protocol became part of new routine care practices.

Sleep Promotion

An interprofessional team consisting of nurses, intensivists, and unit champions identified a designated sleeping time in which the patients were allowed to have at least five hours of uninterrupted sleep. The sleep promotion program consisted of (1) a sleep regimen, (2) patient education, (3) staff education, and (4) a "No Wake Timeframe" of five hours between 11 PM to 4

AM. This timeframe was selected to maximize sleep and balance patient care needs. An environmental assessment identified loud noises, and steps were taken to address them in the ICU. Bundling of nursing care activities reduced sleep interruptions, which promoted sleep, and reduced the risk of delirium. Dimming lights, opening or closing blinds, and turning the TV off were key strategies to promote sleep. The nurses educated patients and their families about the importance of sleep. A sticker was posted outside the patient's room to alert the ICU staff that the patient was on the sleep protocol. Each patient was provided with eye masks and earplugs. Data on adherence to the sleep component of DPB were collected using the compliance data collection tool (Appendix R).

Evaluation Plan

Data were imported into Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 28.0) for analysis. Measures of central tendency described characteristics of patients and nurses (e.g., means, ranges, standard deviations). A two-tailed Pearson's Chi-squared (χ^2) test examined the change in delirium incidence pre and post-DPB implementation. The level of significance was set at alpha equal to 0.05. Nurse survey results were aggregated at the group level (pre-group and post-group) for analysis. Strategies to address DPB implementation barriers were identified and implemented concurrently with data analysis and collection.

Results

The purpose of the project was to reduce delirium incidence and its outcomes by implementing a nurse-led non-pharmacological delirium bundle at a 32-bed community hospital ICU. The results section provides information on primary outcomes (delirium incidence and DPB documentation) and secondary outcomes (ICU LOS, ventilation days, ICU mortality, restraint usage, and nurse-perceived delirium barriers). Baseline patient outcome data were compared with post-implementation outcomes data. The pre-education survey was also compared with the post-education survey to identify barriers to the implementation of the DPB.

Patient Participants

During the three months of this project, between October and December 2022, 160 patients (81 patients pre and 79 patients post) were admitted to the ICU. Sixty-one patients in the pre-intervention group and 61 in the post-intervention group met the inclusion criteria. The patient demographic and clinical data pre and post-groups are provided in Appendix O. The mean age of patients in the pre-intervention group was 64.43 years, 59% were male, and 41% were female. The mean age of patient participants in the post-intervention group was 64.36 years, 61% were male, and 39% were female. The distribution by comorbidities and race/ethnicity are also shown in Table 7 (Appendix O).

Nurse Participants

Table 8 in Appendix T shows the nurse participant demographics. Results were aggregated at the group level (pre-group/post-group). All nurses employed in the unit participated in the education. Pre and post-groups were similar in terms of sex, age, education, and years of experience. Of the 52 nurse participants, 49 (94%) completed the pre-education survey, and 46 (88%) completed the post-education survey. As the aim of the survey was to

determine how the same nurse participants perceived barriers changed after their education. It should be noted that three nurse participants who did not respond to the post-education survey were removed from the analysis. The final sample for analysis comprised 46 nurse participants, 74% were between 30 and 49 years old, and, on average, half worked the day shift. The majority (74%) were female, and 96% worked full-time. Among the nurse participants, 27% had an Associate Degree in Nursing (ADN), 67% held a Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN), and 6% had a Master of Science in Nursing (MSN). Three nurses (6%) held the ICU specialty certification, and 41% had more than five years of ICU experience.

Primary and Secondary Outcomes

The incidence of delirium decreased (36% to 16%, $\chi^2 = 6.10$, $p = .014$) between pre-DPB and post-DPB (Appendix U Table 9; Appendix V Figure 6). The compliance with DPB implementation was 100% (either by EHR documentation or bedside audit). The average ventilation days and ICU LOS did not change between pre and post-implementation. In contrast, both ICU mortality and restraint usage decreased between pre and post-implementation.

Nurse Perceived Delirium Barriers Survey

Before the education sessions, 52% of nurse participants agreed with the statement that the CAM-ICU was complex, whereas, in post-education, 20% agreed that CAM-ICU was complex (Appendix W). In pre-education, 13% of nurses were not confident about using the CAM-ICU, while in post-education, 4% reported not being confident in using the CAM-ICU. Additionally, nurses perceived that screening for delirium using the CAM-ICU was time-consuming had decreased post implementation (74% pre to 9% post). The percentage of nurses who agreed or strongly agreed that screening using CAM-ICU in intubated patients was difficult decreased from 89% pre to 70% post. After education, most nurses agreed that delirium was

underdiagnosed (50% pre to 93% post) and was associated with higher mortality (30% pre to 93% post). Moreover, after education, more nurses agreed that delirium was a common response to the ICU environment (89% pre to 96% post), and the CAM-ICU does improve clinical outcomes (24% pre to 98% post).

Discussion

This DNP evidence-based project aimed to improve delirium incidence by implementing a nurse-led non-pharmacological delirium bundle at a 32-bed ICU community hospital. The importance of this project must be considered in light of the recent changes in the prevention of delirium from a pharmacological to a non-pharmacological approach. The success of this project is reflected in similar projects taken from the literature (Collinworth et al., 2021, Hee et al., 2021; Mart et al., 2021). The literature supports a nurse-led non-pharmacological intervention as effective at reducing the incidence of delirium. The discussion is based on the primary and secondary project outcomes, which were the incidence of delirium, compliance with DPB implementation, ICU LOS, restraint usage, ventilation days, ICU mortality, and barriers to DPB implementation, respectively. The discussion addresses the project's outcomes, cost, implications for practice, and limitations.

Project's Outcomes

Incidence of Delirium

This EBP project demonstrated that a nurse-led non-pharmacological DPB resulted in a 55% reduction in delirium incidence and improved several important patient outcomes (Appendix V). Mart et al. (2021) and Collinsworth et al. (2021) also reported comparable findings when implementing a similar non-pharmacological delirium prevention bundle in their ICU. Furthermore, the project findings were consistent with two meta-analyses, which reported that non-pharmacological delirium prevention interventions significantly reduced the incidence of delirium (Hshieh et al., 2015., Zhang et al., 2020).

Compliance with DPB Implementation

Measurement of compliance with the DPB was more complicated than anticipated. For example, sleep promotion activities were not consistently documented by the day shift nurses in the EHR. However, when unit champions and the PA made informal rounds using the audit tool (Appendix R), sleep promotion activities were noted throughout the unit. Thus, the documentation of DPB compliance was reported as 100% for this project. Regardless of the inconsistency in the documentation of DPB within the EHR, there was a marked improvement in reducing delirium incidence, suggesting that nurses were performing the DPB components even if their documentation was less than optimal at times. Unfortunately, no data were collected that measured the disparity between EHR documentation and PA and clinical champions' bedside audits.

The compliance with the DPB implementation in this project was inconsistent with previous reports of lower compliance with bundles such as ABCDEF (Barnes-Daly et al., 2017; Pun et al., 2020). This discrepancy might be attributed to fewer components in the DPB compared to the ABCDEF bundle, which had six components. Organizing and coordinating a bundle of many components can be challenging in a busy ICU setting. The DPB in this project consisted of only three components, which could have been perceived as not overtly complex: thus, facilitating its implementation. Moreover, as this DPB was nurse-led, without the necessity of requiring a physician's order, the ICU nurses were engaged and enthusiastic to initiate this project. The bundle compliance might also be associated with factors such as effective education, delirium rounding by unit champions, and continuous audits with feedback.

Documentation of the DPB was built into the EHR, which helped to sustain the momentum to implement delirium care. Furthermore, nurses were reminded to implement the

DPB during daily huddles and through emails. Unit posters and bedside training sessions also enhanced motivation for this project. Compliance could have been influenced by the Hawthorne effect, which occurs when individuals improve their performance when others observe them (Sedgwick, 2015). The Hawthorne effect could have happened when unit champions and the PA observed the nurses during audits and daily delirium rounding.

ICU Length of Stay

Despite a significant decrease in the incidence of delirium, this project was unable to reduce ICU LOS. Although some studies have demonstrated a reduction in ICU LOS (Burton et al., 2021; Chia-Hui Chen et al., 2017), it was difficult to determine why the DPB was ineffective for this outcome in the current project. A likely explanation could have been the higher acuity level as reflected in the larger number of comorbidities among patients in the post-implementation phase (more than five comorbidities, 29% pre vs. 36% post). Comorbidity may be a moderate reflection of acuity. Patients with high acuity and several comorbidities tend to stay longer in the ICU than patients with low acuity and fewer comorbidities (Almas et al., 2021). However, this project did not include a formal measure of acuity level. Additionally, four patients in the post-implementation phase had LOS between 10 to 17 days, while the LOS in the pre-implementation phase had only one outlier of 10 days. The post-implementation group also had more patients receiving mechanical ventilation, which could have also contributed to the extended LOS. Future projects should consider the feasibility of using a formal measure of these cofounders pre and post-DPB implementation.

Restraint Usage

The restraint usage decreased in this project. This is consistent with Pan et al. (2018), who also reported reduced restraint use after implementing a multi-component delirium

prevention strategy. The fewer restraint usage might reflect the effect of early mobility, which required the removal of mobility-impeding factors such as restraints, lines, and catheters. This helped to increase patient mobility, thereby limiting the number of restraints a patient was exposed to from 6 to 5 patients post-intervention.

Ventilation Days

In this project, mechanical ventilation days did not decrease after the implementation of the DPB. This contrasts with Hshieh et al. (2015), who reported that implementing a delirium prevention bundle was associated with reduced mechanical ventilation days. However, in a meta-analysis on the effectiveness of bundle interventions to reduce mechanical ventilation days, Zhang et al. (2020) reported that their findings were inconsistent or even contradictory among the studies.

ICU Mortality

The improvement in mortality rates reported in this project is consistent with the research on DPBs (Chia-Hui Chen et al., 2017; Shao et al., 2021; Witlox et al., 2010). A recent meta-analysis highlighted that delirium was associated with increased ICU mortality (Thein et al., 2020). Barnes-Daly et al. (2017) also reported that with every 10% increase in partial bundle compliance, patients had a 15% higher hospital survival. As delirium in the ICU is associated with fatality, there is an urgent need to identify and prevent delirium. Considering that prescription of antipsychotics or sedatives during delirium can increase delirium-associated mortality, educating providers to avoid these medications is essential (Chia-Hui Chen et al., 2017).

Barriers to DPB Implementation

During this project, the ICU nurses positively responded to implementing the CAM-ICU and the DPB. Numerous facilitating factors were implemented to address the barriers identified in the nurse-perceived delirium barriers surveys. Data from the surveys showed that the delirium education and training program successfully improved ICU nurses' delirium knowledge and self-confidence. The results were consistent with Holt et al. (2013), who recognized that nurse education improved competency and skills and reduced delirium incidence and related complications. Teamwork and a multidisciplinary approach were paramount to implementing all the components of the DPB completely and improving the workload. For example, the success of early mobility required multidisciplinary collaboration among nurses, PTs, and RTs. Despite the barriers, this project empowered the nurses to realize the benefits of the DPB among ICU patients.

Cost

A cost analysis that estimates the return on investment facilitates sustainability for a practice change. The cost analysis for this project was limited to hospitalizations ending December 2022. The expenses for implementing this project included educating and training ICU nurses, buying gift cards and stationery, printing CAM-ICU laminated cards, and IT consultation. The healthcare organization approved the cost before the project's initiation. The cost of implementing the project included paying a 30-minute wage, including benefits at an approximate rate of \$65 for 52 nurses who attended the mandatory education. The cost of education was \$1,690. The laminated cards, paper, gift cards, stationery, and IT consultation were evaluated to be \$550. The total cost was \$ 2,240. The education department and the PA

supported these expenses. Reduction of delirium represented a cost saving of \$24,000 for the first month. The return on investment (ROI) is expected to be \$21,760 monthly (Appendix X).

Implications for Practice

The result of the project has important implications for ICU leaders and health policymakers pursuing safer delivery of care. The DPB used in this project, although limited in scope when compared with the ABCDEF bundle, was highly cost-effective and easy to integrate into routine care. To reduce undetected cases of delirium and accelerate delirium prevention bundle implementation, ICU nurses and leaders should be vested in prioritizing delirium care. It is crucial that ICU nurses be aware that delirium is a bedside diagnosis. The most critical step in delirium prevention is the delirium screening for all ICU patients, for which nurses need to use a screening tool such as the CAM-ICU. The delirium screening in the ICU needs to be integrated into all patients' admissions and daily nursing assessments. Moreover, as screening tools such as the CAM-ICU can be initially challenging, ICU nurses must be trained to become competent in using a screening algorithm. Additional evaluations of delirium screening and prevention competencies can be built into annual nursing competency assessments.

Real-time feedback on compliance with screening and full delirium bundle implementation can increase adoption. A comprehensive multimodal delirium education can enhance nurses' knowledge, attitudes, and competency in implementing delirium care. Unit champions, delirium rounding, and interprofessional collaboration are crucial in managing the complexity and adoption of delirium bundles. ICU leaders should address barriers such as lack of resources, competing demands, and poor confidence in implementing the bundle. Ongoing evaluation of processes and outcomes can support sustainability. Broader dissemination of an

evidenced-based delirium prevention bundle in different settings, such as step-down departments and skilled nursing facilities, can reduce the hazards of delirium.

Limitations

There were limitations noted in this project. First, the PA was a leadership team member, which may have inflated nurse/administrator buy-in and accessibility to resources. Regardless, the use of bedside nurses and unit champions within the planning and implementation phases improved nurse engagement and the overall success of the project. Another limitation was the reliability of the data from the EHR. The PA and unit champions depended exclusively on accurate data entry and retrieval from the EHR. Nevertheless, delirium incidence decreased significantly, indicating compliance with the bundle was sufficient to lead to marked improvements in clinical outcomes. Time constraints in this project limited the assessment of long-term sustainability. However, with the clinical success and cost savings of the project, the PA is confident both nurses and administrators will continue to facilitate the practice change. Last, although the findings of the nurse-perceived delirium barriers survey results were based on self-reports, they should be interpreted cautiously due to the potential for overestimating self-perceived confidence and competency and the potential for the Hawthorne effect.

Conclusion

Delirium is a life-threatening emergency, and prevention is key to reducing the burden of delirium on ICU patients. The results of this EBP project suggest that screening all ICU patients with the CAM-ICU and initiating a nurse-led non-pharmacological delirium prevention bundle is feasible and effective in reducing the incidence of delirium and its adverse clinical outcomes. As nurses spend the most time with patients than any provider, they play a crucial role in preventing delirium. Unfortunately, ICU nurses may not prioritize delirium prevention due to a lack of

awareness of delirium symptoms, perceived barriers, time constraints, and workload. Addressing these barriers will optimize delirium screening and the implementation of a DPB. Integrating delirium protocols in the EHR and continuous support and monitoring from unit leaders is essential to sustaining this practice change.

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Appendix A

Table 1: Factors Associated with Delirium

Table 1

Factors Associated with Delirium

Non-modifiable	Modifiable
History of cognitive disorders/dementia	Use of restraints
Male	Use of catheters
Age 70 and older	Pain
Institutional living arrangements	Sleep disruptions
Social isolation	Sensory impairment
Hearing/visual impairment	Decreased mobility
Chronic hypoxia from anemia or COPD	Infections/fever
Major illness/hip fractures/open heart surgery	Hypoxemia
Surgery, acute respiratory distress	Dehydration/malnutrition
	Use of medications known to contribute to the development of delirium
	Anesthesia time over 1 hour
	Low blood pressure/electrolyte disturbances
	Drug/Alcohol abuse

Appendix B

Iowa Authorization Letter

○ Kimberly Jordan - University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics <survey-bounce@survey.uiowa.edu>

Saturday, June 4, 2022 at 21:37

To: ☉ Reesaul, Babita

External Email Use Caution and Confirm Sender

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Reference: Cullen, L., Hanrahan, K., Edmonds, S. W., Reisinger, H., & Wagner, M. (2022). Iowa implementation and sustainability framework. *Implementation Science*, 17, 1-20. <https://proxy.qualtrics.com/proxy/?url=https%3A%2F%2Fdoi.org%2F10.1186%2Fs13012-021-01157-5&token=36AUG9a64VBO%2B%2F8ZmzGWse7vObpgk9%2Fq1xxQxXAGoI0%3D>

Please contact UHCNursingResearchandEBP@uiowa.edu or 319-384-9098 with questions.

Appendix C

Figure 1: Iowa Model

Figure 1

Iowa Model

Appendix D

Table 2: Integration of the Iowa Model

Table 2

Integration of the Iowa Model

Iowa Steps	Action	Organizational System Support: Leadership/Multidisciplinary (MTD)
Knowledge Focused-Tigger	Process Improvement: Inconsistent use of screening tools, prevention, and delirium management strategies	Senior executives involvement Publicize project
Priority for Organization	<p>A stated goal for the ICU and organization was to improve outcomes</p> <p>Highlighted advantages and impact on care</p> <p>Distributed key evidence</p> <p>Reduced the incidence of delirium.</p> <p>Cost-effective care for delirium</p>	Cost implication, financial resources, and adequate technology
Form a Team	Front line nurses, managers, directors, chief nursing officer, intensivists, nurse practitioners, quality departments, IT.	<p>Teamwork and building relationships</p> <p>Benchmark data</p> <p>Informed leaders and higher management</p>
Assemble Research and Literature	<p>Cochrane, CINAHL, and PubMed were reviewed to identify screening tools and DPB.</p> <p>Criteria for screening tool: simple to use and valid.</p> <p>PADIS Critical Care Medicine Guideline</p> <p>Was there sufficient research base? =Yes</p>	

Critique and Synthesis Research for Practice	Created a non-pharmacological bundle Education for nurses and families	
	Analyzed structure, process, and outcome Gap analysis Target Outcomes: incidence of delirium, delirium days, ventilation days, restraint usage, ICU LOS, DPB documentation, Nurse perceived barriers Disseminated evidence with clear implications for practice	Incorporated in the strategic plan
Pilot Change and Evaluation	Collected baseline data and select outcomes to be achieved	Force field analysis to identify restraining and moving forces
	Educated nurses (computer-based, PowerPoint, bedside demonstratons) on case studies	
	CAM pocket guide, resource materials, quick reference guide Implemented EHR to document CAM-ICU and DPB. Reminded staff of CAM-ICU screening every shift	
	Change agent, champions, and role model	Searched for financial support
	Reminders and practice prompts	Incorporated in the strategic plan
Modified the delirium prevention bundle as needed		
To disseminate protocol for CAM-ICU in ER and Medical-Surgical Units		

Fully Implemented and Follow-up	Skill competency, troubleshooting at the bedside, MTD discussion Provided recognition, celebrated ICU progress, personalized message to staff Disseminated results	Revised policy, procedures, and protocols Reported to the quality department and higher management Long-term effect tracking: Audit, feedback, unit orientation Monitored fiscal outcomes
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Appendix E

Figure 2: Confusion Assessment Method for the ICU (CAM-ICU) Flowsheet

Figure 2

Confusion Assessment Method for the ICU (CAM-ICU) Flowsheet

Appendix F

Table 3: Three Components of Delirium Prevention Bundle

Table 3

Three Components of Delirium Prevention Bundle

Three Components of the Bundle	Bundle Activities
	Updating the white board
	Plan of care on white board, date, time, and clinicians' names
	Individualizing bedside area (photographs, painting, books)
	Orientating to surroundings including time, place, date, hospitalization reason
Re-orientation Bundle	Orientation (Every 3 hours) 0700, 1000, 1300, 1600 Cognitive stimulation through activities such as discussing current family life events and reminiscing
	Presence of glasses, hearing aids, dentures
	Therapeutic engagement/Sensory
Early Mobility Bundle	Use safety screen checklist Assess lines/restraints necessity Frequent turning Assist with sitting/transfer to bed/passive ambulation Perform active/passive ROM Mobility team
Sleep Promotion Bundle	Sleep regimen Offer eye mask, ear plugs, blanket Adjust room temperature Dim main ICU lights (11PM-4AM) Open or close blinds, door TV off

Appendix G

Figure 3: Patient Participants' Flow

Figure 3

Patient Participants' Flow

Note: RASS=Richmond Agitation Sedation Scale

Appendix H

IRB Approval

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH

OFFICE OF RESEARCH & SPONSORED PROGRAMS

DATE: September 21, 2022

TO: Babita Reesaul, MSN
FROM: CSULB IRB

PROJECT TITLE: [1947896-1] Screening and Prevention of Delirium in an Intensive Care Unit
REFERENCE #: 23-033
SUBMISSION TYPE: New Project
REVIEW TYPE: Exempt Review

ACTION: APPROVED under 45 CFR 46 Exempt 104(D)(3).
APPROVAL DATE: September 21, 2022

This is to advise you that the Institutional Review Board for the Protection of Human Subjects (IRB) of California State University, Long Beach, has reviewed your protocol application.

Approval is effective beginning September 21, 2022 and conditional upon your willingness to carry out your continuing responsibilities under University policy:

1. If you need to make changes/revisions to this approved project, you must submit a Request for Amendment to an Approved Protocol form in addition to any documents affected by the requested change. Submit these documents as a subsequent package to your approved project in IRBNet. You are not allowed to implement any changes to your research activities prior to obtaining final approval of your Amendment from the CSULB IRB.
2. You are required to inform the Director of Research Integrity and Compliance, Office of Research & Economic Development, via email at ORSP-Compliance@csulb.edu, within twenty-four hours of any adverse event in the conduct of research involving human subjects. The report shall include the nature of the adverse event, the names of the persons affected, the extent of the injury or breach of confidentiality or data security, if any, and any other information material to the situation.
3. Maintain your research records as detailed in the protocol.

Should you have any questions about the conduct of your research under this protocol, particularly about providing informed consent and unexpected contingencies, please do not hesitate to call the Office of Research & Sponsored Programs at (562) 985-8147. We wish you the best of success in your research.

Appendix I

Notice of Informed Consent

Project Title: Screening and Prevention of Delirium in the Intensive Care Unit

Investigator: Babita Reesaul

Project Contact: breesaul@csu.fullerton.edu (562-766-1612)

California State University, Long Beach (CSULB)

Office of Research and Sponsored Programs, CSULB: 1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840

You are invited to participate in a quality improvement study conducted by Babita Reesaul, a Doctor of Nursing Practice student.

The purpose of this study is screening and prevention of delirium in the intensive care unit (ICU). A nurse-led non-pharmacological delirium prevention bundle will be implemented. If you participate in this study, you will be required to complete a basic demographic questionnaire and take a pre and post knowledge quiz. Your responses to the questions will be confidential. The total time of your participation is expected to last around 10 minutes.

There is no risk to participating in this study. You may not directly benefit from participating in this study; however, the results of this study may benefit the ICU patients and its community.

Any information collected from you in this study will be stored in a secure location.

You may contact the Office of Research and Sponsored Programs at ORSPCompliance@csulb.edu, or calling (562) 985-8147, if you have questions about your rights as a research participant.

Signing this document means that all information about the study has been explained to you orally, the investigator has answered any questions you have about the study and that you voluntarily agree to participate.

No, I do not wish to participate in the project.

Name of Subject (Printed)

Subject Signature

Date

Appendix J

Table 4: Nurse Perceived Delirium Barriers Survey

Table 4

Nurse Perceived Delirium Barriers Survey

	Strongly Agree	Moderately Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Strongly Disagree
	5	4	3	2	1
a) CAM ICU is too complex to use					
b) I am not confident to use CAM-ICU					
c) CAM-ICU is too time consuming to perform					
e) CAM-ICU is difficult to evaluate in intubated patients					
f) Delirium is a common response to ICU environment					
g) Delirium is an underdiagnosed problem					
h) Delirium is associated with higher patient mortality					
i) I feel that using CAM-ICU improves patients' outcomes					

Note: CAM-ICU= Confusion Assessment Method- Intensive Care Unit, ICU=Intensive Care Unit

Appendix K

Table 5: Outcome Data

Table 5

Outcome Data

Measure Name	Measure Description
Delirium incidence	CAM positive for at least one day per patient, and only one episode per patient divided by the total participants meeting eligibility criteria
Compliance with documentation of CAMs	Total number of documented CAM divided total number of patients eligible for CAM
Compliance with DBP bundle	Total number of documented DPB divided by total number of participants eligible for DPB
Complete bundle performance (full)	Complete or partial bundle performance were measured on the days that the patients was in the ICU for a full 24 hours. Delivery of all three individual bundle components that a participant received on any given day
Incomplete bundle performance (partial)	Percentage of bundle components performed on a given day
Average Length of Stay in the ICU	Measured from ICU admission date until ICU discharge date or death date divided by total number of patients
Average ventilation days	Total number of ventilator days from the first day of intubation to the last day of extubation divided by total number of patients on the mechanical ventilator
Restraint usage	Reported as No (Absent), Yes (Present)
ICU mortality	Frequency of all-cause of death occurred divided by total number of patients in the sample

Note: ICU= Intensive Care Unit; DPB= Delirium Prevention Bundle

Appendix L

Table 6: Routine Care vs DPB

Table 6

Routine Care vs DPB

	Routine care (Control group – pre-DPB)	DPB
Delirium screening with CAM-ICU	CAM-ICU embedded in EHR	CAM-ICU embedded in EHR
Sleep Promotion	Light turned off after midnight Keep noise down No sleep protocols Staff not educated about sleep promotion	TV off Eye Mask/Ear plugs Sleep protocol
Re-orientation	Orientation in the morning only Not all rooms have clocks Not all patients had their glasses and hearing aids Whiteboard not regularly updated Inconsistent teamwork	Purposeful SoMs Clock in all rooms All patients had glasses and hearing aids Laminated Checklist in rooms Whiteboard regularly updated Team approach and daily rounding
Early mobility	Ad hoc basis No mobility protocol	Purposeful mobility using a protocol Restraints and discontinue catheter as soon as possible

Note: DPB= Delirium Prevention Bundle

Appendix M

Figure 4: Patients and Family Pamphlets

Figure 4

Patients and family Pamphlets

How to Help a Patient with Delirium?

- Speak softly and use simple words or phrases
- Remind the patient of the day and date.
- Talk about family and friends.
- Bring glasses, hearing aids.
- Decorate the room with calendars, posters, or family pictures. These familiar items might be reminders of home.
- Provide the patient with favorite music or TV shows.
- If your loved one has delirium, we might ask you to sit and help calm them.

Delirium is Different From Dementia

Delirium

- Delirium comes on quickly, in hours or days. Signs of delirium can change from one day to the next.
- Delirium can make memory and thinking problems worse.
- Delirium usually clears up after a few days or even a week.

Dementia

- Usually dementia is a permanent condition.
- Dementia is a disturbance of thinking. It comes on over months or even years.
- Patients with dementia are more likely to develop delirium.

People Most Likely to Get Delirium

People who:

- Have dementia
- Are advanced in age
- Have surgery, especially hip or heart
- Have depression
- Take certain high-risk medicines
- Have poor eyesight or hearing
- Have an infection or sepsis
- Have heart failure

DELIRIUM IN THE INTENSIVE CARE UNIT

A Guide for Families and Patients

Como Ayudar a un Paciente Con Delirio

- Hable en voz baja y use palabras sencillas
- Recuérdle al paciente el día y la fecha
- Hable de familia y amigos.
- Traiga sus anteojos y aparatos del oído.
- Decore la habitación con calendarios, carteles o fotografías familiares. Estos artículos familiares pueden ser recordatorios del hogar.
- Póngale al paciente su música o programas de televisión favoritos.
- Si su ser querido tiene delirio, es posible que le pidamos que se siente y ayude a calmarlo.

Delirio es Diferente a la Demencia

Delirium

- El delirio aparece rápidamente en horas o días. Los signos del delirio pueden cambiar de un día para otro.
- El delirio puede empeorar los problemas de memoria y de pensamiento.
- El delirio generalmente desaparece después de unos días o hasta en una semana.

Demencia

- Por lo general, la demencia es una condición permanente.
- La demencia es una alteración del pensamiento. Aparece durante meses o incluso años.
- Los pacientes con demencia son más propensos a desarrollar delirio.

Personas con más probabilidades de obtener Delirio

Personas que:

- Tienen demencia
- Son mayores
- Son sometidos a una cirugía, especialmente de cadera o corazón
- Tienen depresión
- Toman ciertos medicamentos de alto riesgo
- Tienen mala vista o audición
- Tiene una infección o sepsis

DELIRIO EN LA UNIDAD DE CUIDADOS INTENSIVOS

UN GUÍA PARA FAMILIAS Y PACIENTES

What is Delirium?

The word "delirium" is used to describe a severe state of confusion.

People with delirium:

- Cannot think clearly
- Have trouble paying attention
- Have a hard time understanding what is going on around them
- May see or hear things that are not there. These things seem very real to them.

Delirium is common. About 2 out of 3 patients in ICUs get delirium.

7 out of 10 patients get delirium while they are on a breathing machine or soon after.

DELIRIUM IS ASSOCIATED WITH THINKING AND MEMORY PROBLEMS THAT CAN LAST FOR MONTHS.

A Recipe to Build Your Own Toolbox

Sleep Promotion

- Eye masks
- Ear plugs
- Relaxation TV channel

Environment

- Light switch (reminder to turn lights on and open shades during day and turn off/close at night)

Sensory Improvement

- Hearing aid batteries
- Eyeglass wipes
- Reader glasses
- Magnifier
- Engagement of Family
- Puzzles
- Crayons
- Playing cards
- Large print word search or crossword puzzle
- Stuffed animal

Additional Information and Resources

- Music
- Recorded familiar voices

Causes of Delirium

Experts think delirium is caused by a change in the way the brain is working.

This can be caused by:

- Less oxygen to the brain
- The brain's inability to use oxygen
- Chemical changes in the brain
- Certain medicines
- Infections
- Severe pain
- Medical illnesses
- Alcohol, sedatives, or pain killers
- Withdrawal from alcohol, nicotine

Signs of Delirium

Your family member may:

- Appear agitated or even quiet
- Be confused
- Be aggressive
- Use inappropriate words
- Not be able to pay attention or follow directions
- Be unsure about where they are
- Be unsure about the time of day
- See things that are not there
- Act different from usual
- Have changes in sleeping habits
- Have emotional changes
- Have movements that are not normal, like tremors or picking at clothes
- Have memory problems

Que es el Delirio?

La palabra "delirio" se usa para describir un estado severo de confusión.

Personas con delirio:

- No puede pensar claramente
- Tienen problemas para prestar atención
- Tienen dificultad para entender lo que sucede a su alrededor.
- Puede ver u oír cosas que no están allí. Estas cosas les parecen muy reales.

El delirio es común. Alrededor de 2 de cada 3 pacientes en ICU tienen delirio.

7 de cada 10 pacientes tienen delirio mientras están conectados a un respirador o poco después.

EL DELIRIO ESTÁ ASOCIADO CON PROBLEMAS DE PENSAMIENTO Y MEMORIA QUE PUEDEN DURAR MESES.

Una receta para construir tu propia caja de herramientas

Promoción del sueño

- Mascaras para los ojos
- Tapones para oídos.
- Canal de televisión relajante

Ambiente

- Interruptor de luz (recordatorio para encender las luces y abrir las persianas durante el día y apagar/cerrar durante la noche)

Melora Sensorial

- Baterías para aparatos de oído
- Toallitas para lentes
- Lentes para leer
- Lupa
- Participación familiar
- Rompecabezas
- Crayones
- Jugando a las cartas
- Búsqueda de palabras en letras grandes o crucigramas
- Pelucho

Información Adicional y Recursos

- Música
- Grabar voces conocidas

Causas del Delirio

Los expertos creen que el delirio es causado por un cambio en la forma en que funciona el cerebro.

Esto puede ser causado por:

- Menos oxígeno al cerebro.
- La incapacidad del cerebro para usar oxígeno.
- Cambios químicos en el cerebro.
- Ciertos medicamentos
- Infecciones
- Dolor severo
- Enfermedades medicas Alcohol, sedantes o analgésicos
- Abstinencia de alcohol, nicotina

Signos de delirio

Su familiar puede:

- Parecer agitado o incluso tranquilo
- Estar confundido
- Ser agresivo
- Usar palabras inapropiadas
- No puede prestar atención o seguir instrucciones.
- No estar seguro de dónde están
- No estar seguro de la hora del día
- Ver cosas que no existen
- Actuar diferente de lo habitual
- Tener cambios en los hábitos de sueño.
- Tener cambios emocionales
- Tener movimientos que no son normales, como temblores o rascarse la ropa
- Tiene problemas de memoria

Appendix N

Safety Screen for Early Mobility

- a. Patients are candidates for early mobilization when the following [minimum] criteria are met:
 1. Neurologic: patient responds to verbal stimulation (RASS > or equal -3)
Activity will not be started on comatose patients (RASS -4 to -5).
 2. Respiratory FiO₂ (Fraction of Inspired Oxygen) less than 60%.
PEEP (Positive End Expiratory Pressure) less than 10 cmH₂O
 3. Circulatory/central lines/contraindications
Absence of vasopressor infusions for at least 2 hours
Absence of active myocardial ischemia
No arrhythmia requiring the administration of NEW antiarrhythmic
Not receiving therapy that requires restriction in mobility such as femoral arterial lines, or open abdominal wounds
No injuries for which mobility is contra-indicated
- b. Any other justification for not initiating early mobilization must be ordered by a physician or intensivist
- c. The interdisciplinary care team will assess the patient's readiness for mobilization. The team includes physical therapist who assesses the patient's physical ability to participate; a nurse assessed physiological stability; and a respiratory therapist who is responsible for maintaining the patient's airway. The physician will provide any other reasons for mobilizations contraindications.
- d. Each patient is assessed on arrival in the ICU. Those who qualified are immediately placed on the early mobility protocol. Those who are determined not to meet criteria will be reevaluated daily.

Criteria for Discontinuing Mobilization Therapy includes:

- Symptomatic or drop in mean arterial blood pressure
- Heart rate less than 50 or greater than 130 beats per minute for 5 minutes
- Respiratory rate of less than five or greater than 40 breaths per minute for 5 minutes
- Blood pressure greater than 180 mmHg for 5 minutes
- Pulse oximetry less than 88% for 5 minutes
- Marked ventilator efforts
- Patient distress
- New cardiac arrhythmias
- Concern for myocardial ischemia
- Concern over airway integrity
- Fall to knees
- Endotracheal tube removal

Appendix O

Table 7: Patient Demographics

Table 7

Patient Participants' Demographics (N=122)

	Pre-DBP implementation (n=61)	Post-DBP implementation (n=61)
Age mean +/-SD	64.43 (±15.137)	64.36 (±17.535)
Sex		
Male n (%)	36 (59%)	37 (61%)
Female n (%)	25 (41%)	24 (39%)
Comorbidities on admission n (%)		
< 3	16 (26%)	14 (23%)
3-5	27 (44%)	25 (41%)
>5	18 (30%)	22 (36%)
Ethnicity		
Non-Hispanic n (%)	32 (53%)	37 (61%)
Hispanic n (%)	29 (47%)	24 (39%)
Race		
Caucasian n (%)	34 (56%)	41 (67%)
Non-Caucasian n (%)	27 (44%)	20 (33%)

Note: DPB= Delirium Prevention Bundle, SD = Standard Deviation

Appendix P

Figure 5: Project Timeline

Figure 5

Project Timeline

Appendix Q

Electronic Health Record Documentation

Bundle 1 (Re-orientation) ? x

Date/Time | 102622 | 0827 | Current

Assessment Type Initial Shift

Scrip - Script reading Q3 hours	Full - Full bundle implemented
White - White board:Plan of care	Parti - Partial bundle Implemented
Famil - Familiarize/individualized bedside area	Unabl - Unable to implement bundle
Orien - Orient to surroundings,reason,date&time.	
Thera - Therapeutic engagement,family life events	
Impro - Improve sensory - glasses & hearing aids	

< Prev Cancel Clear Update Next >

Touch abbreviations prior to manual entry.

Bundle 2 (Early & Frequent Mobility) ? x

Date/Time | 102622 | 0827 | Current

Assessment Type Initial Shift

Evalu - Evaluation of patient readiness	Full - Full bundle implemented
Evalu - Evaluate restraints and line necessity	Parti - Partial bundle test
Compl - Completing active & passive ROM	Unabl - Unable to implement bundle
Assis - Assisting with sitting at edge of bed	
Activ - Active transfer to chair	
Fassi - Passive ambulation	

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Touch abbreviations prior to manual entry.

Bundle 3 (Sleep Promotion) ? x

Date/Time | 102622 | 0828 | Current

Assessment Type Initial Shift

Imple - Implement sleep regimen	Turn - Turn TV off
Eye m - Eye mask/earplugs/blanket offered	Full - Full bundle implemented
Bundl - Bundle care activities	Parti - Partial bundle implemented
Adjus - Adjust room temperature	Unabl - Unable to implement bundle
Dim m - Dim main ICU lights (11PM-4AM)	
Open - Open or close blinds & doors	

< Prev Cancel Clear Update Next >

Touch abbreviations prior to manual entry.

Appendix R

Bundle Compliance Data Collection Tool

	CAM-ICU Pos/Neg	RASS	Re-orientation	Early Mobility	Sleep Promotion	Rounding Yes/No
Patient 1	Pos <input type="checkbox"/> Neg <input type="checkbox"/>		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Patient 2	Pos <input type="checkbox"/> Neg <input type="checkbox"/>		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Patient 3	Pos <input type="checkbox"/> Neg <input type="checkbox"/>		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Patient 4	Pos <input type="checkbox"/> Neg <input type="checkbox"/>		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Patient 5	Pos <input type="checkbox"/> Neg <input type="checkbox"/>		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Patient 6	Pos <input type="checkbox"/> Neg <input type="checkbox"/>		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Patient 7	Pos <input type="checkbox"/> Neg <input type="checkbox"/>		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Patient 8	Pos <input type="checkbox"/> Neg <input type="checkbox"/>		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Patient 9	Pos <input type="checkbox"/> Neg <input type="checkbox"/>		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Patient 10	Pos <input type="checkbox"/> Neg <input type="checkbox"/>		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Patient 11	Pos <input type="checkbox"/> Neg <input type="checkbox"/>		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Patient 12	Pos <input type="checkbox"/> Neg <input type="checkbox"/>		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Patient 13	Pos <input type="checkbox"/> Neg <input type="checkbox"/>		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Patient 14	Pos <input type="checkbox"/> Neg <input type="checkbox"/>		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Patient 15	Pos <input type="checkbox"/> Neg <input type="checkbox"/>		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	

Appendix S

Script of Messages (SoMs)

Hello _____ (Name of patient). This is nurse _____

1	You are at _____ Regional Medical Center
2	Our team is here to help you
3	The machines are making noises, but they are here to help you.
4	Your wrists are attached to prevent you from pulling tubes or wires.
5	You cannot talk because you have a tube that is helping you to breathe.
6	Please be calm so that we can help you get better.
7	Your family knows you are here, and we are helping you.

(Spanish)

Hola _____ (Nombre os paciente). Soy su enfermera/o _____

1	Usted está en el hospital de ██████ Regional.
2	Nuestro equipo está aquí para ayudarle.
3	Las máquinas están haciendo ruidos, pero están aquí para ayudarle.
4	Sus manos están atadas para evitar que jale los cables o tubos.
5	No puede hablar porque tiene un tubo que le está ayudando a respirar.
6	Por favor, mantenga la calma para que podamos ayudarle a mejorar.
7	Su familia sabe que está aquí y que le estamos ayudando.

Appendix T

Table 8: Nurse Participant demographics (n=46)

Table 8

Nurse Participant demographics (n=46)

Demographic Characteristic	Categories
Age (years)	22 – 29 = 9% 30 – 39 = 35% 40 – 49 = 39% 50 – 59 = 13% 60 – 69 = 4%
Sex	Male = 26% Female = 74%
Credentials	ADN = 27% BSN = 67% MSN = 6%
Certifications	CCRN = 6%
ICU experience (years)	0-1 =20% 1-5 = 39% 6-10 = 13% >10 = 28%
Shift	Day =43% Night=57%
Work Status	Full time=96% Part-time=4%

Note: ADN = Associate Degree in Nursing; BSN = Bachelor of Science in Nursing; MSN= Master of Science in Nursing; CCRN=Certified Critical-Care Nurse

Appendix U

Table 9: Outcome Measures

Table 9

Outcome Measures

Measure	Pre-DBP implementation (N=61)	Post-DBP implementation (N=61)	Statistical Analysis
Delirium Incidence (n, %)	22 (36%)	10 (16%)	$\chi^2 = 6.10$, df = 1, p=.014
CAM-ICU Documentation (n, %)	61 (100%)	61 (100%)	
Number of Restraints (n, %)	6 (9.8%)	5 (8.2%)	
ICU Mortality (n, %)	8 (13.11%)	4 (6.55%)	
Average Ventilation Days (Days, SD)	3.4 (± 2.351)	3.54 (± 2.750)	
ICU LOS, (Median)	4.00	4.00	

Note: *DPB*= Delirium Prevention Bundle, *p*=probability statistics, *SD*=Standard Deviation, χ^2 = Chi Square test, *df* = degree of freedom, *ICU LOS* = Intensive Care Unit Length of Stay, *CAM-ICU*- Confusion Assessment Method-Intensive Care Unit

Appendix V

Figure 6: Delirium Incidence

Figure 6

Delirium Incidence

Note: DPB= Delirium Prevention Bundle

Appendix W

Table 10: Response Results to Nurse Delirium Barriers Survey

Table 10

Response Results to Nurse Delirium Barriers Survey

	Agree Pre*	Agree Post*
	N=46	N=46
CAM-ICU too complex	24 (52%)	9 (20%)
Not confident to use CAM-ICU	6 (13%)	2 (4%)
CAM-ICU is too time consuming to perform	34 (74%)	4 (9%)
CAM-ICU difficult to use when ventilated	41 (89%)	32 (70%)
CAM-ICU improves outcomes	11 (24%)	45 (98%)
Delirium common in ICU	41 (89%)	44 (96%)
Delirium underdiagnosed	23 (50%)	43 (93%)
Delirium patients have higher mortality	14 (30%)	43 (93%)

Note: *strongly & moderately agree versus all other responses, *ICU* = Intensive Care Unit, *CAM-ICU* = Confusion Assessment Method-Intensive Care Unit, *N*=number

Appendix X

Table 11: Cost Outcomes

Table 11

Cost Outcomes

Item	Description	Total Cost	Comments
Expenses			
Training/education of 52 RNs	30 minutes	\$1,690	Average hourly rate equals \$65 (including benefits)
Paper & stationery		\$100	
IT (EHR integration)		\$300	
Gift cards		\$150	
Revenue			
Decreased in delirium incidence (12 days less @ \$2000/day)	Amount potentially saved with reduced delirium incidence	\$24,000	